
DISCOURSE OF CLIMATE CHANGE IN THE NOVEL ‘ORYX AND CRAKE’ BY MARGARET ATWOOD

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Annotation. Climate change produces its own discourse, with terms like *land use*, *climate extreme*, and *deforestation*. Yet we also find that it renders certain words redundant. The article begins by discussing the origins of language in natural phenomena. By detailing how language, and thus meaning, comes into being through a phenomenological relationship with the land, we can understand how changes in the landscape might affect our vocabulary. It then discusses the contemporary eco-novel *Oryx and Crake* (2003), and this analysis of the novel highlights the importance of being able to name our natural world and foregrounds the consequences when this is no longer possible. It also provides examples from the novel to illustrate how pervasive this theme is across climate novels, and as an opportunity to gain a more detailed sense of the genre in general.

Keywords: Climate change, climate novels, eco-novel, cognition, consciousness, environment.

Introduction

Climate novels are central to the process of fastening ‘words to visible things,’ allowing us to speak about and be attentive to our environment and thus enchant us towards an ecological imagining. Climate novels can also weave the new, mostly scientific, technical or economic, discourse generated by climate change into meaningful and relevant stories. These novels help us explore and understand the greater consequence of climate change beyond the physical, such as the troubling ontological consequences it can entail. The emphasis is also for the novel to integrate the emerging climate discourse into its stories so that the issue might be contemplated in a more immediately relevant and thought-provoking way. We need to generate an evocative discourse of climate change so that it does not remain as mere terminology.

Methodology

In order to understand the ways in which climate change can alter words, we can look towards wider theories concerning the formation of human cognition and language in relation to the environment. These theories highlight the symbiosis between language, being, and environment. Hegel’s idea about the formation of consciousness in relation to objects offers a useful starting point. Hegel suggested

that selfhood is determined by perceptual engagement with external phenomena. This challenges the dichotomy between mind and matter and the related idea that consciousness is a preformed, transcendental entity housed simply in the body. Hegel argues that ‘consciousness is, on the one hand, consciousness of the object, and on the other, consciousness of itself’.[5. p.54] He explains that ‘sense-certainty’ is a primitive form of consciousness in which the object is immediately present. This then mutates into perception, and then perception into understanding. Hegel’s outline of the stages leading to understanding highlights how the self is formed in conceptual relation. Edward Soja extends Hegel’s notion further by applying it to spatiality. As with Hegel, Soja notes that ‘spatiality is present at the origin of human consciousness’.[3. p. 133] Soja claims that the first created space, the distance between subjective consciousness and object, forms the basis to our being. Being arises in the interplay between subjectivity and objectivity.

Soja’s idea of ‘emplacement’ introduces us to the concept that being and understanding are reliant on spatiality and phenomena. In other words, consciousness is dependent upon a material ‘lifeworld’.

The anthropologist Tim Ingold similarly notes that our existence begins within our environment. Ingold discusses the shift in anthropological thought from the idea of cultural knowledge as something imported into a setting, to an understanding that it is rather constituted within it. His work asserts that cultural knowledge is built from activity in the environment. Ingold emphasises the importance of bodily experience: meaning is not allocated by the mind to phenomena but arises in lived action: ‘in short, far from being inscribed upon the bedrock of physical reality, meaning is immanent in the relational contexts of people’s practical engagement with their lived-in environments.’[11. p. 168] Ingold explains that a place gains its meaning by the people and organisms that dwell there, through a process of incorporation and not inscription. He offers an interesting distinction between environment and landscape, the former is the objective, physical reality, made up of neutral objects, whilst the latter, landscape, is constituted in relation to those that inhabit it.

The relationship between consciousness and phenomena can be extended further to understand the original formation of language. David Abram’s *The Spell of the Sensuous* offers an insightful overview of the reciprocal relationship between humans and nature, explaining how language is formed within this sensual interdependence. Abram’s work renews the school of phenomenology within the context of the current environmental crisis. Abram positions himself as an environmental activist and suggests that in order to prevent ecologically destructive behaviour we must ‘reanimate’ our perception to include a conscious engagement with the environment. Abram’s work examines the importance of the nonhuman component within the configuration of language, meaning and forms of identification. His thinking

establishes the importance of ecology to the health and development of our intellect. His work demonstrates that the ecosystem – land, weather, atmosphere, and species – is paramount to our capacity to know and define. Abram’s statement that ‘we are human only in contact, and conviviality, with what is not human’, [2. p. 9] is an important notion. We find, form and understand our humanness in relation to that which is external and other to us. Without this, our capacity to think and act as humans is diminished.

Abram argues that language originates in our sensual experiences of the world, and, furthermore, suggests that the motions, shapes, sounds and colours of nature are a basis to the formation of language:

“Human languages, then, are informed not only by the structure of the human body and the human community, but by the evocative shapes and patterns of the more-than-human terrain. Experientially considered, language is no more the special property of the human organism than it is an expression of the animate earth that enfolds us.”[2. p. 90]

These notions from Hegel, Soja, Ingold and Abram help us to understand how a primary form of consciousness and language originates through interaction with place. We find that our sense of perception is formed through a relationship with the natural world. These ideas are important for understanding how changes in place might impact on our ability to draw meaning, and I illustrate this notion through my close reading of the novels. The following analysis intends to underpin some wider philosophical notions that are general across this thesis, concerning the importance of nature not only as a means of sustenance, but also as core to our ontological wellbeing. The novel present extreme, post-apocalyptic, versions of environmental destruction. The disasters may not necessarily be a result of climate change, and, their causes are unclear. But their representation of environmental destruction and its effects upon the characters’ ability to name is useful here. In my readings of the novel I suggest that certain processes of climate change and the destruction of nonhuman life corresponds to a loss of referents.

Results and Discussion

Narrated from both before and after a disaster, *Oryx and Crake* provides a fable about unchecked human interference with nature. Nature ceases to exist in its original sense, since everything is artificially recreated or controlled. Society is divided by those who live inside the compounds, and those who do not. Life is equally bleak, whether in the crime-ridden slums or inside the artificial and despotic compounds. Crake responds to this nightmare by deciding to eliminate its human cause by developing a plague. Only Jimmy is spared, whom Crake keeps alive to become a guardian for his new and eco-friendly species of humans, the ‘Crakers’, created to inhabit what now remains of the world. We first believe that Jimmy, or Snowman as

he later renames himself, is the only survivor, but by the end of the novel it has become clear that others have remained alive. Despite Crake’s belief that he has perfected a new human race able to live without tendencies towards domination, crime and harmful attitudes to the environment, his experiment ultimately fails, as the ‘Crakers’ begin to imitate destructive human behaviour. Hannes Bergthaller’s analysis of the novel suggests that it is ‘principally concerned with the question of what role language, literature and, more generally, the human propensity for symbol-making can play in our attempts to deal with the ecological crisis’.[6. p. 729] Elaine Showalter also notes the importance of language and imagination in the novel, highlighting their importance for thinking about solutions to ecological issues. [4. p. 35]

A simple understanding of ecology tells us that biotic health thrives and exists only in relation to other species and natural processes: the greater the biodiversity the greater the thriving of the community. Variety is vital within ecology, yet it also vital for meaning in words and the prosperity of selfhood. We can find parallels to this mechanism in the functioning between language, self and ecology. In ecology the extinction of a species impacts upon the rest of its environment and can lead to a domino-like elimination of creatures, plants and habitats. [1. pp. 59-67] This same subsuming destruction takes places in language, as words shrink and disappear alongside other living things in the environment. As certain terms become redundant through ecocide, the language network begins to break down and gaps in vocabulary increase the inadequacy of other terms. *Oryx and Crake* show how this linguistic collapse begins with the nouns of physical entities and then extends to more abstract notions, which cease to make sense without relation or reference to other things. In the novel, Jimmy’s questioning reflects this relationship: ‘can a single ant be said to be alive, in any meaningful sense of the word, or does it only have relevance in terms of its anthill?’, [9. p. 429] he asks, which suggests that meaning only exists through its relationship with other things and is diminished when aspects of its context are destroyed. Within a system of interconnection, obliteration becomes selfperpetuating and degrades more rapidly with each further loss. Due to this chain-like structure, more breaks in the chains lead to a greater loss of meaning and it becomes increasingly difficult for thought to function. The whole structure finally becomes entirely obsolete when the links become too tenuous for this chain of relevance and meaning to continue to exist, as Crake remarks to Jimmy:

“‘All it takes,’ said Crake, ‘is the elimination of one generation. One generation of anything. Beetles, trees, microbes, scientists, speakers of French, whatever. Break the link in time between one generation and the next, and it’s game over forever.’” [9. p. 262]

Jimmy experiences the destruction of the environment as a loss of words, which become increasingly redundant in the destroyed or artificial landscape:

“What’s happening to his mind? He has a vision of the top of his neck, opening up into his head like a bathroom drain. Fragments of words are swirling down it, in a grey liquid he realizes is his dissolving brain.” [9. p. 175]

There are many instances throughout the novel depicting Jimmy’s attempts to preserve his vocabulary:

“He memorized these hoary locutions, tossed them left-handed into conversation: *wheelwright, lodestone, saturnine, adamant*. He’d developed a strangely tender feeling towards such words, as if they were children abandoned in the woods and it was his duty to rescue them.” [9. p. 230]

The narrative is frequently intersected with Jimmy’s listing of words:

“He compiled lists of old words too – words of a precision and suggestiveness that no longer had a meaningful application in today’s world...”[9. p. 230]

“Rag ends of language are floating in his head: *mephitic, metronome, mastiltis, metatarsal, maudlin...*[9. p. 175]

“Then he’d stay up too late, and once in bed he’d stare at the ceiling, telling over lists of obsolete words for the comfort that was in them. *Dibble. Aphasia. Breast plough. Enigma. Gat...*”[9. p. 306]

These anxieties over the disappearance of language reflect how environmental destruction affects as both an ecological and linguistic crisis. It becomes more difficult for him to maintain his lists. As his environment is damaged, either by technological manipulation, pollution or extinction, words become increasingly displaced:

“From nowhere, a word appears: *Mesozoic*. He can see the word, he can hear the word, but he can’t reach the word. He can’t attach anything to it. This is happening too much lately, this dissolution of meaning, the entries of his cherished wordlists drifting off into space.” [9. p. 43]

The words become more elusive. Without physical counterparts, or with more gaps in the chain, certain words fall to redundancy without a context in which to exist. Jimmy recognises the importance of maintaining these words since he understands that with their disappearance his sense of meaning is also threatened. His environment is first destroyed and then his means to understand it fades away, too. The more seemingly tenuous and superfluous words are the most important ones to preserve, since these seem to suffer the most dramatically in the loss of thought:

“‘Hang on to the words,’ he tells himself. ‘The odd words, the old words, the rare ones. *Valence. Norn. Serendipity. Pibroch. Lubricious*. When they’re gone out of his head, these words, they’ll be gone, everywhere, forever. As if they had never been.’” [9. p. 78]

Jimmy tries to preserve these words and recognises their value beyond simply being a means to order and objectify the world, but as the very basis of sense and bringing one’s self in relation with that which is external. His word lists temporarily offer comfort in his increasing separation from the world, its comfort all the more important as he believes he is the only one of his own species left. Yet it occurs to him that the task is pointless when the words eventually exist as mere sound patterns, without use or referent:

“But there was no longer any comfort in the words. There was nothing in them. It no longer delighted Jimmy to possess these small collections of letters that other people had forgotten about. It was like having his own baby teeth in a box.” [9. p. 307]

For Jimmy this simultaneous destruction of the environment and language also presents itself as an obliteration of thought: “I used to be erudite,” he says out loud. *Erudite*. A hopeless word. What are all those things he once thought he knew and where have they gone?’ [9. p. 175]. He claims that ‘there are a lot of blank spaces in his stub of a brain, where memory used to be’ [9. p. 5]. One of Jimmy’s observations is particularly important: ‘But he doesn’t know which it is, bigger or smaller, because there’s nobody to measure himself by. He’s lost in the fog. No benchmarks’ [9. p. 279]. This encapsulates the precise problem of his crisis, as there are ‘no benchmarks’ in a world in which the environment has been so utterly destroyed, forms of measure are lost, sending its survivors into an inconceivable existence. Nature offers measure and points of comparison through its variety and otherness. When this becomes lost, we have fewer means for creating understanding.

Oryx and Crake is positioned within the absence of constructed time. As the novel begins, ‘A blank face is what it shows him: zero hour. It causes a jolt of terror to run through him, this absence of official time. Nobody nowhere knows what time it is’ and ends: ‘From habit he lifts his watch; it shows him its blank face. Zero hour’ [9. pp. 3 & 433]. Jimmy exists in a realm of abstraction, as nouns for time become irrelevant, ‘in September or October, one of those months that used to be called *autumn*’ [9. p. 81]; he can neither determine the time of year nor name it. As a result, Jimmy feels he cannot belong to the present:

“On some non-conscious level Snowman must serve as a reminder to these people, and not a pleasant one: he’s what they may have been once. *I’m your past*, he might intone. *I’m your ancestor, come from the land of the dead. Now I’m lost, I can’t get back, I’m stranded here, I’m all alone. Let me in!*” [9. p. 123]

Jimmy is unable to make sense of an environment that is so radically altered. His previous conceptions of the world are becoming increasingly inapplicable. Ecocide results in Jimmy’s existential crisis.

Conclusion

Climate change alters language, but language can shape and enrich our sense of place. The natural world forms a basis to our language, as depicted in the novels, however, ecocide withdraws a certain capacity to name or gather ‘benchmarks’ from the environment and the protagonists experience a diminution of their vocabulary. Climate change generates its own discourse; with many scientific terms to describes its processes, as well as various policy and technological terms for thinking about mitigation strategies. Such new diction needs to become part of our cultural and creative imaginings in order for us to respond to and consider the importance of climate change. Macfarlane shows us how we already have a rich vocabulary for naming our environment, and it is one that can enchant us with place and help counteract environmentally destructive behaviours. These particular words assist with developing an ecological consciousness. However, their use is declining and they are in danger of being lost.

We find, that a particular diction is needed for speaking about climate change. It needs to be poetic and rich to draw us into to relation with the environment and contemplate the sense of loss associated with its destruction. The words must also be specific and local; this avoids the oversimplification of climate change endemic in many representations and carves a greater sense of place. The outcomes of this chapter suggest the centrality of language, with its environmental symbiosis and ability to forge ecological enchantment. The climate novel then becomes a critical means to develop such language, consolidating a sense of place and imaginatively recasting the discourse of climate change.

References:

1. Bradley J. Cardinal and others, ‘Biodiversity Loss and its Impact on Humanity’, *Nature*, 486 (2012).
2. David Abram, *The Spell of the Sensuous* (London: Vintage Books, 1997).
3. Edward W. Soja, *Postmodern Geographies: The Reassertion of Space in Critical Social Theory* (London: Verso, 1989).
4. Elaine Showalter, ‘The Snowman Cometh’, *The London Review of Books*, 25 (2013).
5. G. W. F. Hegel, *Phenomenology of Spirit*, trans. by A. V. Miller (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1977, [1807]).
6. Hannes Bergthaller, ‘Housebreaking the Human Animal: Humanism and the Problem of Sustainability in Margaret Atwood's *Oryx and Crake* and *The Year of the Flood*’, *English Studies*, 91 (2010).
7. Lowe, Thomas, and others, ‘Does Tomorrow Ever Come? Disaster Narrative

8. and Public Perceptions of Climate Change’, Tyndall Centre Working Paper,
9. 72 (2005).
10. Macfarlane, Robert, ‘The Burning Question’, The Guardian. 24 September
11. 2005.
12. Margaret Atwood, *Oryx and Crake*, (London: Bloomsbury Publishing PLC, 2003).
13. Merleau-Ponty, Maurice, *Phenomenology of Perception*, trans. by Donald A.
14. Landes (New York: Routledge, 2012).
15. Tim Ingold, *The Perception of the Environment: Essays in Livelihood, Dwelling and Skill* (New York: Routledge, 2000).